

Photobromination of Cinnamic Acid and Stilbene.

Part III.

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In Part II of this series it was shown that the velocity of this photochemical reaction in green and blue light is given by the equation,

$$k\sqrt{I_0} = \frac{1}{t} \log_e \frac{a}{a-x} + \frac{1}{t} \frac{1}{(c-a)B} \log \frac{a(c-x)}{c(a-x)}$$

where I_0 is the incident intensity, a is the initial concentration of bromine, c is the initial concentration of acceptor molecules and B is a constant given by $Aa^2\tau k\theta$, where a is the distance between the centres of two reacting molecules, τ is the life period of excited molecules, θ the absolute temperature, $k=p/c\theta$ (p is the osmotic pressure in millimeters of mercury, and c the concentration in gram. mol.

per litre) and $A=2666.6 \sqrt{\frac{2\pi N}{K} \cdot \frac{m_1+m_2}{m_1 m_2}}$.

This reaction also takes place in yellow light, but as it is to be expected from the weak absorption of yellow light by the bromine solution, the rate of reaction is given by a modified equation. The concentration of $[\text{Br}]$ i.e., active bromine atom is chiefly determined by the reversible reaction, $\text{Br} + h\nu \rightleftharpoons 2\text{Br}$, and is therefore given by the equation,

$$[\text{Br}] = \sqrt{k \cdot I_0 (1 - e^{-\epsilon [\text{Br}_2] l})}$$

For weak absorption

$$[\text{Br}] = \sqrt{k I_0 \epsilon [\text{Br}_2] l} = \sqrt{k' I_0 [\text{Br}_2]}$$

The mechanism of the reaction that has been developed in Part II will therefore give the equation,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k\sqrt{I_0}\sqrt{(a-x)}(a-x)\frac{\tau}{T+\tau} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$= k\sqrt{I_0}(a-x)^{\frac{3}{2}}\frac{B(c-x)}{1+B(c-x)} \quad \dots (3)$$

On integration

$$k = \frac{1}{t} \left\{ \frac{1}{(a-x)^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{1}{a^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right\} + \frac{1}{3Bt} \left[\frac{1}{(a-x)^{\frac{3}{2}}} - \frac{1}{a^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right] \dots (4)$$

If Berthoud's mechanism were correct the velocity constant would have been given by the equation

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \left\{ \frac{1}{(a-x)^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{1}{a^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right\} \quad \dots (5)$$

In the following tables are given experimental data which prove definitely that equation (4), and not (5), represents the course of this photochemical reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Experimental procedure is exactly the same as described before.

Yellow light was obtained by using the following filters recommended by Plotnikow.

(1) Potassium permanganate solution—0.375 g. per litre (1 cm. thick).

(2) Potassium chromate solution—150 g. per litre (1 cm. thick).

(3) Nickel sulphate solution—300 g. per litre (2 cm. thick),

Solvent—CS₂; Acceptor—cinnamic acid;

Initial conc. of cinnamic acid—0.01515 M;

Initial concn. of bromine—0.01515 M;

Temperature—29°C; B=120.

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TABLE I.
Incident intensity 1305 ergs. per sq. cm. per sec.

Time in min.	(α - α) conc. Br ₂ : gm. mol./litre.	k_1 (from Eqn. 5)	k (from Eqn. 4)
0	·01515	...	...
10	·01133	·128	·210
20	·00902	·120	·208
30	·00733	·118	·216
46	·00580	·109	·213
71	·00430	·100	·213

TABLE II.
Incident intensity 810 ergs. per sq. cm. per sec.

0	·01515	...	...
10	·012	·100	·160
20	·0099	·0989	·160
35	·00805	·096	·153
50	·00632	·0807	·153
70	·00534	·0796	·160

TABLE III.
Incident intensity 270 ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

0	·01515	..	...
30	·01213	·0427	·0723
46	·00984	·0425	·0720
69	·0083	·0412	·0724
94	·0070	·0407	·0753 (?)

Solvent CS₂ ; Acceptor—stilbene ;
Initial conc. of bromine—0·01515 M.
Initial conc. of stilbene—0·01515 M.
Temperature 29°C; $B=360$.

TABLE IV.

Intensity 1805 ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

Time in mins.	(a-x) conc. Br ₂ : gm. mol./litre.	k ₁ (from Eqn. 3)	k (from Eqn.4)
0	01515	...	...
15	01105	0918	112
30	0085	0908	114
45	0068	0898	115
66	00523	0864	116

TABLE V.

Intensity 810 ergs. per sq. cm. per sec.

0	01515	...	...
20	01098	0713	0875
40	0085	0681	0852
66	00635	0670	0871

TABLE VI.

Intensity 270 ergs.. per sq. cm. per sec.

0	01515	...	...
30	01185	0855	0428
60	00954	0850	0433
90	00803	889	0427
132	0065	.385	0433

The dependence of the velocity constant on the incident intensity of illumination is given in the following table.

TABLE VII.

Acceptor.	Intensity.	Ratio of velocity constants.	Ratio of intensity.
Cinnamic acid	1805 ergs.	from (1) & (2) 1'85	1'26
	810 ergs.	from (1) & (3) 2'9	2'2
	270 ergs.	from (2) & (3) 2'1	1'73
Stilbene	1805 ergs.	from (1) & (2) 1'81	1'26
	810 ergs.	from (1) & (3) 2'65	2'2
	270 ergs.	from (2) & (3) 2'02	1'73

From the above results it is evident that the velocity constant increases more rapidly than the square root of the incident illumination.

The temperature coefficient of the reaction in yellow light has been measured and found to be 3.1. The results of measurements of the temperature coefficient in blue and green light (Part II) showed that the temperature coefficient increases with the wavelength of incident radiation. The measurements in yellow light also corroborate this.

Induction Period and After-effect.

It had already been noticed that the reaction passes through a period of induction; the induction period however, in no case is large. It was considered interesting to find out if the reaction is accompanied by an after-effect. It was probable that the active bromine atom or intermediate complex containing bromine would undergo quick transformation in the dark after the illumination is cut off, the reaction ceasing altogether when the active molecular species are completely transformed into stable molecules. It is very difficult to study accurately the velocity of this rapid transformation after cutting off the light. The following tables contain some of the experimental observations. It may be mentioned here that the velocity of reaction in the dark when the period of after-effect is over is very small.

Blue Light.

(Filters as recommended by Plotnikow)

Conc. of bromine—0·01515 M.

Conc. of cinnamic acid—0·01515 M.

Solvent CS₂ ; Temperature 29°C.

TABLE VII.

Time in minutes.	($\alpha-x$) conc. Br ₂ : gm. mol./litre.	Rate of disappearance of Br ₂ in the successive intervals (in one minute).
0	·01515	
3	·01395	·0006
6	·01125	Exposed to light. ·0007
9	·0099	·00078
12	·0078	·0007
Light cut off.		
30	·0067	Darkness ·000061
100	·0062	·0000085

Solvent CS₂. Initial concentration of bromine—0·01515 M.

Initial conc. of stilbene—0·01515 M.

TABLE IX.

Time	($\alpha-x$) conc. of Br ₂ : gm./mol. litre.	Rate of disappearance of Br ₂ in the successive intervals.
0	·01515	...
3	·01405	·00037
6	·01265	Exposed to light. ·00047
9	·01095	·00057
12	·00930	·00055
Light cut off.		
22	·0082	Darkness ·00011
55	·0078	·000012

TABLE X.

Solvent CCl_4 . Initial conc. of Br_2 —0.01515 M.
Initial of conc. of cinnamic acid—0.01515 M.

0	01515		
5.5	0136	Exposed to light.	00028
11	0119		00081
16	0103		00034
Light cut off.			
45	0094	Darkness.	.000028
105	0081		000005

From the above results it is clear that in the case of these reactions, the induction period is followed by an after-effect when the source of illumination is withdrawn. Another interesting fact has been observed. It appears that if the reacting system is again exposed to light after the induction period and after-effect are over, the reaction passes through another short period of induction. This observation clearly proves that there must be some intermediate complex formation in the process of photobromination. Berthoud's method of varying light intensity by the use of rotating sector is, in this case, open to an obvious objection; because the successive period of induction and after-effects would certainly prevent the attainment of equilibrium between the various reacting unstable intermediate molecules which take part in the process of photo-bromination.

